

Dynamical Stability and Parameter Selection in Neural Optimization

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Abstract

Finding suitable parameter values in solving optimization problems with the Hopfield net is of crucial importance. In this paper we present a systematic approach, based on analyzing dynamical stability of valid solutions, for finding relationships among the parameters which make their selection much easier. Furthermore, this technique can show whether the problem formulation is flawed. As an example we discuss the Hopfield-Tank formulation of the Traveling Salesman Problem and show that it is dynamically unstable, hence obtaining valid solutions are difficult. We also discuss the modified formulation by Aiyer, et al. which overcomes the instability problems.

1 Introduction

Since the work of Hopfield and Tank [6] on the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP), the neural net approach has become a popular technique for solving optimization problems with combinatorial complexity. This approach has been intensively investigated and extended by many researchers to solve a variety of problems with varying degrees of success (for example, see Proceedings of Conferences on Neural Networks from 1986 onward). In this neural net approach the problem is formulated in terms of an energy function, composed of cost and constraint terms, whose minima are the valid solutions; with the deepest minimum corresponding to the best solution. The energy function has several free parameters that must be set before the network is run. Improper parameter values can drastically affect the network performance in that it may become unstable and thus unable to find valid solutions. Selection of parameter values is usually based on intuitive arguments and often involves a laborious procedure of trial and error.

In this paper we present a systematic method for selecting the parameter values. The method is based on analyzing dynamical stability of valid solutions, which yields relationships among the parameters. These relations show that the parameter values cannot be arbitrary, thus the search space for parameter values becomes greatly restricted and, therefore, finding optimal values becomes much less tedious. In the next section we describe this approach, and in section 3 demonstrate its application with an example, namely the Hopfield-Tank formulation of the TSP problem.

In formulating a problem in terms of a neural network, one usually uses heuristic arguments. The dynamical stability analysis we present here can also show whether in the given formulation valid solutions are stable, i.e. whether valid solutions can be found at all. If valid solutions turn out to be dynamically unstable, then the formulation needs to be modified. As an example, again we consider the Hopfield-Tank TSP formulation and show that all valid solutions are unstable, hence the formulation is flawed. We also consider the modified formulation by Aiyer, Niranjana, and Fallside [1] and show that it is dynamically correct.

2 Dynamically Stable Valid Solutions

In the Hopfield-Tank approach to solving an optimization problem, the problem is formulated in terms of the energy of a network, whose minima are possible solutions. The energy, $E(V)$, is typically composed of cost and constraint terms. Here $V = (V_1, \dots, V_N)$, where V_i is the output

activity of neuron i and N is the number of neurons in the network. The dynamics of a network of analog neurons are given by the set of N coupled ordinary differential equations,

$$\frac{du_i}{dt} = -\frac{\partial E}{\partial V_i}, \quad \text{where } V_i = g(u_i). \quad (1)$$

Here u_i is the input potential of neuron i , and $g(u_i)$ is the neuron gain function. It can be shown [2,5] that the time rate of change of the energy is

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = -\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial V_i}\right)^2 g'(u_i).$$

Hence if $g(u)$ is a nondecreasing function, then the energy is a Lyapunov function, i.e. $dE/dt \leq 0$, thus the network starting from any initial state converges to a minimum and finds a solution. The gain for analog neurons is often chosen to be the sigmoid function given by

$$V_i = g(u_i) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \tanh \frac{u_i}{u_0}\right), \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dV_i}{du_i} = g'(u_i) = \frac{2}{u_0} V_i(1 - V_i), \quad (2)$$

where u_0 is the gain parameter. In such a network valid solutions (i.e. those solutions that minimize the constraint terms alone) are near certain corners of the N -dimensional unit hypercube, which is the state space of the network.

For a problem that can be encoded as a quadratic function of the activities the energy takes the following form:

$$E(V) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N T_{ij} V_i V_j - \sum_{i=1}^N I_i V_i + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\tau_i} \int^{V_i} dz g^{-1}(z). \quad (3)$$

where $T_{ij} = T_{ji}$ are the elements of the connection matrix, I_i are the neuron biases, and τ_i is the self-decay time of neuron i . The last term models the leakage from neurons and is equal to $\sum \frac{u_0}{2\tau_i} [V_i \ln V_i + (1 - V_i) \ln (1 - V_i)]$ for g given by (2). This term is negligible if u_0 is small, i.e. steep gain, or when τ_i is large, i.e. slow leakage. The dynamics for this network are given by

$$\frac{du_i}{dt} = -\frac{u_i}{\tau_i} + \sum_{j=1}^N T_{ij} V_j + I_i. \quad (4)$$

In this problem solving approach the energy function is handcrafted to balance cost and constraint terms. Thus there are free parameters, appearing in T_{ij} and I_i , whose values must be set before the network is run. The common practice in selecting parameter values is through experimentation, which is tedious and often not optimal. There is, however, a systematic approach for parameter selection based on analyzing dynamical stability of the network, which yields relationships among the parameters, thus making the search for best values much easier. Furthermore, stability analysis shows whether the encoding of the problem in terms of the neural net is accomplished correctly. Below, we give a general description of this approach and in the next section demonstrate its application with an example.

Since the energy is a Lyapunov function its minima, which are valid solutions, are dynamical fixed points. (In the Hopfield-Tank approach constraints are *soft* [10], hence the energy has unwanted minima that violate the constraints.) If valid solutions are to be found by the network, i.e. if the network is to converge to these fixed points, they must be stable.

For analyzing the stability of dynamical fixed points one has to examine the eigenvalues of matrix J whose elements are

$$J_{ij}(u) = \frac{\partial}{\partial u_j} \frac{du_i}{dt}. \quad (5)$$

For the quadratic energy function (3) this matrix is

$$J_{ij} = -\frac{1}{\tau}\delta_{ij} + T_{ij}g'(u_j), \quad (6)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. Now, if u^* is a stable fixed point, then $J(u^*)$ must have no eigenvalues with positive real part [4]. However, extracting useful information from such an analysis is in general a formidable task because: (i) matrix J is large, $N \times N$, hence we must find its eigenvalues numerically, i.e. we must already set the parameter values; (ii) to compute $g'(u_i)$ we must know the precise location of the fixed point, which in turn depends on the parameter values; and (iii) there are a very large number of valid solutions, e.g. about $n!$ for the n -city TSP, for which this analysis must be repeated.

To avoid these difficulties we examine stability of the corresponding digital neural net. A digital neuron is either *on* or *off*. The network dynamics are given by

$$u_i = \sum_{j=1}^N T_{ij}V_j + I_i, \quad \text{with} \quad V_i = \Theta(u_i), \quad (7)$$

where $\Theta(u) = 0$ if $u \leq 0$, and 1 if $u > 0$, is the Heaviside step function. There are fundamental differences between analog and digital networks, namely the dynamics of the digital net are asynchronous and the energy is not necessarily Lyapunov [7]. However, for stability analysis of valid solutions these differences are irrelevant. Now, if V^* is a stable fixed point, then all the V_i^* that are on (off) must stay on (off). That is, we must require

$$u_i^* \leq 0 \quad \text{if} \quad V_i^* = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad u_i^* > 0 \quad \text{if} \quad V_i^* = 1. \quad (8)$$

Again it appears that inferring any useful information about parameter values from these inequalities is hopelessly cumbersome. Because, if there are M valid solutions, then the number of such inequalities will be $N \times M$ — a huge number. For example, in the n -city TSP problem there are n^2 neurons and $n!/2n$ solutions, i.e. over $n!$ inequalities; and for the problem of partitioning n points among k clusters there are kn neurons and about $k^n/k!$ solutions, i.e. over k^n inequalities. However, as we shall see later most of these inequalities have similar forms, thus we need to analyze only a few inequalities. To illustrate this approach we treat the Hopfield-Tank formulation of the TSP problem in the next section. Other examples may be found in [9].

3 The Traveling Salesman Problem

In the n -city problem there are $n!/2n$ distinct possible tours with different lengths. A valid tour may be represented by a permutation matrix; for example a tour for a 5-city problem is shown in Table 1. Based on this representation of the solutions, Hopfield and Tank [6] cast the problem in terms of the following energy function:

$$E = \frac{A}{2} \sum_x \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} V_{xi}V_{xj} + \frac{B}{2} \sum_i \sum_x \sum_{y \neq x} V_{xi}V_{yi} + \frac{C}{2} (\sum_x \sum_i V_{xi} - n)^2 + \frac{D}{2} \sum_x \sum_{y \neq x} \sum_i d_{xy} V_{xi} (V_{y,i+1} + V_{y,i-1}). \quad (9)$$

Indices x and y refer to cities; i and j refer to days and are modulo n ; the sums run from 1 to n ; and d_{xy} is the distance between cities x and y . The A , B , and C terms enforce the constraints imposed by the permutation matrix representation of solutions, while the D -term gives the tourlength. The elements of the permutation matrix are the activities of neurons and when neuron (x, i) is on, i.e. $V_{xi} = 1$, it means that city x is visited on day i .

To select suitable values for parameters A , B , C , and D , we analyze the dynamics of the corresponding digital network which are given by

$$u_{xi} = -A \sum_{j \neq i} V_{xj} - B \sum_{y \neq x} V_{yi} - C (\sum_y \sum_j V_{yj} - n) - D \sum_{y \neq x} d_{xy} (V_{y,i+1} + V_{y,i-1}). \quad (10)$$

Table 1: The permutation matrix representing the 5-city tour ADCBEA.

City	Day				
	1	2	3	4	5
A	1	0	0	0	0
B	0	0	0	1	0
C	0	0	1	0	0
D	0	1	0	0	0
E	0	0	0	0	1

Consider the 5-city problem and suppose the solution given in Table 1 is a stable fixed point which means that at the next time step it must remain unchanged. That is, all neurons that are on (off), e.g. neuron A1 (A2), must stay on (off). Hence the input potential calculated from (10) for neurons A1, A2, and A3 must satisfy the following:

$$u_{A1} = -D(d_{AD} + d_{AE}) > 0, \quad (11)$$

$$u_{A2} = -A - B - D(d_{AC}) \leq 0, \quad (12)$$

$$u_{A3} = -A - B - D(d_{AD} + d_{AB}) \leq 0. \quad (13)$$

Similar inequalities are obtained for all other neurons. Also, for other valid solutions we obtain similar inequalities. Inequality (12) is generally weaker than (13) and can be ignored. Thus all the innumerable inequalities reduce just to the following:

$$D(d_{xy} + d_{xz}) < 0 < A + B + D(d_{vw}). \quad (14)$$

Note that $l = d_{xy} + d_{xz}$ is the length of two successive city distances in a tour, while d_{vw} is any intercity distance in that tour. If these conditions are not satisfied for a given tour, then that tour is unstable and cannot be found by the network.

The Hopfield-Tank Formulation is Unstable

Note that the left inequality in (14) cannot be satisfied by any valid tour, since parameter D and all intercity distances are positive. To be able to find valid solutions, Hopfield and Tank replace the bias $I_{xi} = Cn$ — the constant term in (10) — with an effective bias $\tilde{I}_{xi} = C\tilde{n}$. Thus (14) becomes

$$D(d_{xy} + d_{xz}) < C(\tilde{n} - n) < A + B + D(d_{vw}). \quad (15)$$

Obviously one must take $\tilde{n} > n$, as Hopfield and Tank set $\tilde{n} = 15$ for the 10-city problem. However, this is a deliberate violation of the constraints as the network is encouraged to have more neurons active than is permitted. Indeed, this is the main cause of the network's failure in finding valid solutions [8,12].

For the parameter values $A = B = 500$, $C = 200$, $D = 500$, and $\tilde{n} = 15$ used in [6] for the 10-city problem (15) reduces to

$$d_{xy} + d_{xz} < 2 < 2 + d_{vw}. \quad (16)$$

The right inequality is satisfied, and the left inequality implies that tours with two successive legs $l = d_{xy} + d_{xz} < 2$ are stable and should be found. For cities distributed uniformly within the unit square this is a fairly lax criterion which includes most of the tours (on the average $l = 2/\sqrt{n} = 0.63$ which is substantially less than 2), yet only a few percent of trials yield valid tours [8]. This is because replacing n with \tilde{n} in order to stabilize valid solutions forces the network to violate the constraints.

The extensive empirical studies of the network sensitivity carried out by Davis [3] confirm our theoretical analysis and can be explained by (15). For lack of space we briefly discuss only certain aspects here. For the Hopfield-Tank formulation, Davis finds the percentage of trials that yield valid solutions as a function of \tilde{n} for selected parameter values. In all cases no valid solutions are found if $\tilde{n} \leq n$, in agreement with the left inequality of (15). As \tilde{n} increases the percentage of valid solutions increases, because the sum of two successive legs, $l = d_{xy} + d_{xz}$, can be greater thus a larger number of tours become stable. However, for some value of \tilde{n} the percentage of valid solutions reaches a maximum; this is because although satisfying the left inequality of (15) is becoming easier yet at the same time the network is forced to have \tilde{n} neurons on (instead of n) which is a violation of the constraints. Finally, as \tilde{n} is further increased the percentage of valid solutions drops to zero which is a direct consequence of the violation of the right inequality of (15). For example in the $n = 15$ case, with parameter values $A = B = 500$, $C = 200$, and $D = 300$, the percentage of valid solutions is zero for $\tilde{n} = 22.5$. The right inequality in (15) for this case reduces to $d_{vw} > 5/3 = 1.67$, which implies that at least one leg in the tour must be greater than 1.67. This is impossible for cities within the unit square because the maximum intercity distance is $\sqrt{2} = 1.41$, hence no valid tour can be stable for this set of parameter values.

The Modified Formulation

Aiyer, Niranjan, and Fallside [1] consider an approximate form of (6), where they neglect the cost term and replace g' with a constant. In an elegant treatment they obtain the eigenvectors of the Hopfield-Tank connection matrix with $D = 0$, and show that for the network to move monotonically toward the subspace of valid solutions the connection matrix must be modified. This modification results in the following energy function:

$$E = \frac{A}{2} \sum_x \sum_i \sum_j V_{xi} V_{xj} + \frac{A}{2} \sum_i \sum_x \sum_y V_{xi} V_{yi} - \tilde{A} \sum_x \sum_i V_{xi}^2 + \frac{\tilde{C}}{2} (\sum_x \sum_i V_{xi})^2 - Cn \sum_x \sum_i V_{xi} + \frac{D}{2} \sum_x \sum_{y \neq x} \sum_i d_{xy} V_{xi} (V_{y,i+1} + V_{y,i-1}), \quad (17)$$

where \tilde{A} is a new parameter and $\tilde{C} = C - \frac{2(An - \tilde{A})}{n}$. Since row and column constraints have equal importance B is set equal to A . The dynamics of the corresponding digital net are given by

$$u_{xi} = -A \sum_j V_{xj} - A \sum_y V_{yi} + 2\tilde{A} V_{xi} - \tilde{C} \sum_y \sum_j V_{yj} + Cn - D \sum_{y \neq x} d_{xy} (V_{y,i+1} + V_{y,i-1}). \quad (18)$$

With analysis similar to (11)-(13), we find that the off neurons yield

$$D(d_{xy}) + \frac{2}{n} \tilde{A} > 0, \quad (19)$$

which is always satisfied and is uninformative, while the on neurons give

$$D(d_{xy} + d_{xz}) < \frac{2(n-1)}{n} \tilde{A}. \quad (20)$$

For the 10-city problem, Aiyer, et al. use $A = 8$, $\tilde{A} = 0.25$, $C = 0.8$, and $D = 1$. This implies that only those tours that have two successive legs $l = d_{xy} + d_{xz} < 0.45$ can be stable. We ran this modified network using the 10-city data given in [6] with these parameter values. In 100 trials the network found 21 valid solutions, all with $l < 0.45$ in agreement with (20). Of the 21 solutions: 5 were the best tour with tourlength $L = 2.71$, 3 the second best tour with $L = 2.78$, 3 the third best tour with $L = 2.79$, and the remaining with tourlengths less than 3. When we ran the network with $\tilde{A} = 0.5$, out of 100 trials 81 converged to valid solutions all with $l < 0.9$, again confirming the validity of (20).

4 Concluding Remarks

We have presented a systematic method, based on analyzing the dynamical stability of valid solutions, for selecting network parameter values. This technique yields a number of inequalities among parameter values, which restricts the search space thus making their selection much less tedious. Another benefit of this technique is that it can show whether a given formulation is dynamically stable, or if the formulation needs to be modified. This technique complements the study of network dynamics based on the eigenvectors of the connection matrix as suggested by Aiyer, et al [1].

Another parameter in the neural net approach to solving optimization problems is the gain function parameter u_0 . This parameter is closely related to the *temperature* of the network [10], and the best way to treat it appears to be an annealing strategy [11].

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